

Urgent Computing service in the PRACE Research Infrastructure

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Abstract

The document presents the background and assumptions of the pilot deployment of the Urgent Computing environment in the PRACE RI. It presents several possible scenarios of integrating the functionality bearing in mind that the PRACE RI is a distributed environment with distinct policies, requirements and local limitations. The final recommendations and guidelines will be presented in the project deliverable.

1. Design prerequisites

The goal is to demonstrate the pilot installation of the environment ready to use for the Urgent Computing (UC). To implement specific solutions several possible scenarios were proposed of integrating the prospective functionality into PRACE-RI under the general agreement of the PRACE Technical Board and Board of Directors. The power of PRACE-RI is distributed so it imposes on us a non-uniform behaviour in terms of managing a new service, which is expected to be a single coherent user environment designed to run the applications in question. First, the authors focused on balancing pros and cons regarding available ideas [7], [8], [9]. In parallel, the authors touched technical and local policy aspect on selected test sites (PRACE Exec Sites); PSNC, ICHEC, SURFsara, BSC.

The technical outcome of the document confirms the feasibility of running urgent computing application (UC Application) on each considered PRACE-RI site. The conclusion includes that the recommended policy involves three main steps:

1. An appropriate software is installed on a dedicated EXEC Host.
2. The User of UC Application can operate in normal PRACE Project mode, as, e.g., DECI project, but:
3. UC Application should start as quickly as agreed in the policy agreement. Here it must be agreed on the means to enter into the extraordinary state of the scheduling basing on the configuration provided in advance.

Each of the aforementioned points is split into smaller entities and treated distinctly in the following chapters. The conclusion is the following:

1. Executing UC Application does not violate any PRACE-wide policy.

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2. Exploitation of the UC Application will require the availability of a licensing agreement with the owner of such an application as well as input data by EXEC Host or PRACE-wide.
3. It might happen that memory requirements of a UC Application are over-exhausted, due to the specification of the computational nodes. Some EXEC Hosts do not have virtual memory configured on OS level at all (e.g., PSNC).

2. Important differences between regular jobs and UC jobs

As PRACE is an HPC infrastructure designed for research, the compute-only part of most of its supercomputers is not fault-tolerant against several sorts of hardware failure and certainly not against power failures^b. Since redundancy and fault tolerance is not for free, and hardware and power failures occur quite infrequently, it is more cost-efficient to spend money on total capacity and to simply reschedule and rerun the jobs that have suffered from an occasional failure than to spend more money on resilience and redundancy.

On PRACE systems it is also customary that maintenance intervals are planned and announced in advance, without giving users a back-up production site during maintenance^c. If the announcements are well in advance, this is no problem for regular research jobs. For UC jobs the matter is quite different. It is a defining hallmark for the context of UC that the demand is only foreseeable for a short period prior to execution. Means to synchronize, by delaying or speeding up the course of certain events, may be lacking altogether. The urgency usually implies that there is no second chance. Starting a job after the deadline has past or having to rerun a failed job will make the result, although correct, useless simply because it is too late.

3. Organizing coarse-grained redundancy of systems in stand-by for UC

It is not realistic that the design and maintenance practices of the PRACE HPC infrastructures will be changed significantly to accommodate to the specific requirements of urgent computing. The fault tolerance needed to mitigate the risk that an urgent computing task fails to meet its deadline is thus best served by a “coarse-grained” redundancy: operational platforms for a selected UC case should be implemented on more than one sites^d. The probability that all sites involved must go into unplanned maintenance at the same time is small. The probability that they all have planned maintenance at the same time would be decreased too, but could of course be ruled out, if sites that are peers in supporting UC cases would coordinate and adjust their planned maintenance sessions to the effect that maintenance session do not overlap. While the organization of cross-site coarse-grained redundancy is vital, this should of course not preclude other enhancements of fault tolerance at the site level.

Implementing an operational platform supporting a UC case implies that the systems are each in a state of “warm standby” for the real event. The term “warm standby” was borrowed from the SPRUCE frequently asked questions list [2]. To be, and remain, in a state of warm standby:

- All needed application software must be pre-installed
- One or more data sets suitable for validation must be pre-installed
- There must be a validation protocol using pre-installed software and pre-installed data.
- Runs to execute the validation protocol must be scheduled regularly basing on accepted SLA to verify that the applications keep performing as expected, especially after system changes, software upgrades on general purpose and computational libraries, etc.
- Validation runs can be regular batch jobs. A budget of sufficient core hours to perform these jobs regularly must be allocated.
- Since pre-installed software and data may be damaged by human error, or hardware malfunctioning, or even the above noted updating of other software components, there should also be regularly tested

^b Datacentres do have solutions like diesel powered emergency power aggregates to overcome net outages, but not at the scale to support their relatively power intensive compute-only equipment, which is often only protected against short peaks and dips.

^c Planned complete service outages can range from several minutes or hours, e.g., in the case of system wide software or firmware updates, to several days in the case of major hardware replacements.

^d The principle to have a set of systems that each may fail to offer continuous availability for UC cases, to increase the probability of actual availability when needed. Having more redundant systems minimises the lack of results problem, but increases the maintenance of UC environment. The number of redundant systems must be a part of SLA.

procedure to quickly restore – reinstall, relink, recompile, reconfigure, whatever applies – the pre-installed components.

While validation of the software can blend in with the regular production environment, the workflow of a real event will inevitably need more:

- Platforms supporting a UC case must have a mechanism to raise the emergency flag which can be executed by a pre-selected class of users: UC users, UC operators.
- The raising of the emergency flag must enable the availability of the required compute and storage resources in due time.
- What the exact amount of required compute and storage resources actually is, and what exactly is due time, is of course dependent of the UC task, but must be agreed upon in advance by the involved parties supplying and using the platform.
- How the freeing of adequate resources in due time is implemented should be at the discretion of the platform supplying side. Some sides may want to use pre-emption of already running jobs, others may, e.g., have a sufficiently large dedicated partition for jobs with a fairly short wall clock time that they can drain from regular job usage.
- Complete workflow scenarios, including the actual provisioning of resources in due time, must be regularly practiced as “dry runs” as well.
- The regular testing of workflow scenarios is potentially much more disruptive of normal production work than the above mentioned regular software validation. Its frequency must be agreed upon in advance, at the acceptance of a UC project. The budget in core hours allocated for a UC project should be sufficient to cover the actual loss of computing resources allocated for the regular jobs runtime.

Note that, while this model for UC relies on the independence of execution sites to provide coarse-grained redundancy, further attention must be given to single points of failure which may not be obvious but would effectively couple two or more independent sites with a single dependency. Examples of this may be the network routing path used to propagate input datasets or the remote initiation of UC jobs. Similarly, if the input data sets originate from a single source this is an obvious single point of failure. Any core PRACE infrastructure component or service which is required for authentication or access must also be considered for the architecture.

4. Urgent Computing project and user administration

If the PRACE infrastructure is used to accommodate UC requirements, the best way to go about it is probably to do so by a project-based resource allocation, since this is how PRACE resources for scientific research are normally allocated as well. The administrative machinery needed for project administration is in place, although it may need a little “UC-specific” tweaking. Administratively speaking, a UC project should resemble a regular PRACE project as much as possible. The authoritative guide on “how to go about” administering UC projects then is the PRACE AAA Administration Guide. AAA is an acronym for “Authentication, Authorization, Accounting”. The version of this documented consulted in [5].

Users, of UC applications installed on the PRACE infrastructure will only get access to compute and storage resources if they have been entered into the PRACE user administration and are recognized as valid users by the respective PRACE sites. UC users will have to be integrated into the PRACE public key infrastructure, with a valid personal certificate[°] as the sound basis for authenticated access to resources. Some UC users may be granted privileges that enable them to pre-emptively deny resources to others. And, like any other user, they will be personally accountable for compliance of their actions with the various acceptable use policies that are in place. The fact that UC users may not be associated with organizations that are PRACE partners does not need to be a problem. In fact, the PRACE user administration already has the concept of a “Home organisation of the user” in place that is (re-)usable for UC as well:

This is the PRACE partner organisation responsible for the registration of the user (referred to as Home site). It is not the organisation the user belongs to [5].

[°] Theoretically, the certificate could also be replaced by a public ssh key, but in practice there is currently no solid public key infrastructure system in which certificate authorities can vouch for an ssh key, revoke an ssh key, etc., in the way they can for a digital certificate.

The home site of a user is usually also the home site of the project, but this does not have to be the case in general. The home site of a project is the PRACE partner organisation, assigned by the project review process, to be responsible for the management of the project [5]. There can be only one home site for a specific project. This does not necessarily need to be the execution site of the project, i.e., the site where the project is executed. For PRACE sites operating Tier-0 systems the situation with scientific computing projects is usually quite simple, in so far that the home site of the project, the home site of all the users associated with the project, and execution site are in practice all the same Tier-0 site. For Tier-1 (DECI) projects however, which are administered in the same project and user administration, it is quite common that home site and execution site – or sites, there can be more than one – are different.

The recommendation for UC projects includes:

- They have only one project home site,
- There is the possibility that a user registered by a different home site can be added to a project,
- That, for reasons of redundancy, UC projects have *at least two execution sites*.

This implies that some Tier-0 sites that become execution sites for a UC project will *not* be the home site for that project. There is nothing in the PRACE user and project administration that is not prepared for this situation. It just means that the administrative details of UC projects will bear more resemblance with Tier-1 projects than with the regular scientific projects that have been assigned to Tier-0 systems so far.

5. The selection and acceptance of Urgent computing projects

The selection of relevant and justified UC projects is an entirely different topic than the administrative and technical accommodation of selected projects. Procedures for the latter can be left to the operations side, but the former clearly does not belong there. Such requests must come forward in calls for proposals and can subsequently be granted or denied on the basis of the outcome of reviews and prioritisation criteria.

PRACE has established review procedures for a scientific and technical assessment and a body to organise these assessments – the Scientific Steering Committee. The results of the scientific and technical assessments, performed by peer scientists, are forwarded to an Access Committee that makes recommendations about resource allocation, and hence, in the face of scarceness of resources, in effect makes prioritisation recommendations to the PRACE Board of Directors [3]. The bodies are filled with scientists and the relative ranking for regular research projects competing for resources is determined by the scientific excellence and technical feasibility of the project and the confidence in the technical ability of the applicants.

For UC projects, scientific soundness and technical feasibility as well as an assessment of the applicant's ability to adequately carry out the project, can be done in the same way by the same bodies. And it should be just as stringent, if not more stringent, because there is more at stake. The moral responsibility and perhaps even judicial liability, involved in stating, on the basis of simulation runs, that a particular dam is strong enough to hold in a storm that is rapidly approaching a coast line, and that there is no need for evacuation, is of a very different order than stating something about the nature of gravitational waves or some astrophysical phenomena. On the other hand, it is not only a moral but also an economical question. A month-long gravitational wave simulation run can be more expensive than a breaking dam, if caused loss is minimal (e.g., no affected creatures).

But the selection of UC projects cannot be on regular PRACE-DECI criteria alone. An assessment of the societal urgency and scope of the problem addressed is important as well. However, the assessment of what exactly is of (more) beneficial to society is highly subjective and more of an ideological, moral or political nature. And matters become even more controversial if one has to take into account whether the societal benefits are in the class that should be supported by means of European public expenditure, or by resources provided by national or regional bodies, or should be left to the market. It is not evident that those making assessment about scientific and technical merits should also be the ones making such political assessments. But according to current documentation of PRACE peer review, they could be. On the role of reviewers it states:

*Scientific reviewers will provide a report on the novelty and quality of the science proposed, its potential impact and on the applicant's ability to carry it out. **They will also assess the proposal based on its relevance to any pre-defined criteria for a particular call [4].***

The possibility to propose an UC project should be explicitly addressed in calls for project access as well as calls for programmatic access, but not in calls for preparatory access. The political or moral criteria that demarcate the scope of societal benefits to address and that are used in assessing and prioritizing social benefits must be made explicit upfront as much as possible. In this white paper the author focus on the technical aspects of resource allocation for UC only.

Irrespective of the nature of additional criteria, calls for preparatory access do not seem appropriate for UC applications. There is a tension, if not an outright contradiction, between on the one hand, being urgent and highly relevant in emergency situations, and on the other hand, being experimental, at least in terms of scalability, and not being quite ready for regular production runs. Research on applications that might become relevant for UC is research, not UC. It should compete for resources and priority on regular criteria with other regular projects.

6. Testing and Validation

When designing an architecture for an Urgent Computing model which could potentially be adopted by PRACE, it will be instructive to implement a proof of concept trial, which takes the most important elements of the proposed model above, and deploy it on a number of independent systems. The degree to which this trial incorporates as many components of the model as possible is important because the primary difficulty of a UC model is in overcoming operational limitations and complexity as well as issues surrounding resource contention. For example, if two dedicated “sandbox” clusters are used with no other users or no integration with PRACE services, then it would be relatively straightforward to achieve good results due to a lack of realistic operational workloads or the ability to pre-empt running jobs. However, this highly artificial environment would bear little resemblance to a real-world implementation and so any conclusions would largely be irrelevant due to the substantial deviations from realistic conditions in every-day operations.

For this reason, a proof of concept trial implementation should seek to incorporate as many of the following components as possible:

6.1. Suitable application to execute.

The focus of this trial concerns first of all the workflow and so the details of a particular application are not of primary importance. Required is an application (or set of applications) which possess the characteristics of a UC application [10], [11]. The single most important characteristic is that it needs to be a distributed memory code, which runs over a relatively large number of nodes (or else there would be no need to use PRACE resources). The code should be compute (or communications) bound and possibly require linking against performance math and scientific libraries. Examples of candidates include weather forecasting, flash flood, earthquake early warning system, tracking real-time storms, storm surge computation, forest fire propagation, etc.

For testing purposes only, a dummy application generating real machine load is used. Since the authors do not own a real UC Application, the decision was taken to run test code of three sizes on selected production systems:

- 256 cores,
- 128 cores,
- 32 cores.

The assumption is that UC software fits into physical memory space of MPP or cluster architecture.

6.2. Two or more PRACE Tier-1 sites willing to contribute a small amount of resources to this test, plus a third site acting as the client to submit and monitor UC jobs.

A critical component of the model proposed above is the use of independent sites to run the UC application simultaneously. These sites should be operational with realistic workloads from multiple users running a variety of applications and job sizes. To add further elements of real world complexity, both sites should preferably use different batch scheduling software. A third site is required which will represent the home site of the UC user and will initiate data staging and trigger job execution and data retrieval. In case of an emergency a person permitted to trigger the UC application will be allowed to do it from pretty much everywhere, as long as she can provide the necessary ID.

The execution sites will be required to make modifications to the batch scheduling configuration to enable UC jobs to start as quickly as possible. At least this will require an elevated job priority or QOS and could extend as far as job pre-emption if the site is willing and able to support this.

The following EXEC Site modes have been evaluated regarding LRMS batch policy modifications:

- SLURM (SURFsara, PSNC)
- Torque/Moab (ICHEC)
- LSF (BSC)

6.3. PRACE user credentials

To simulate the user access methods such as GSI-SSH, gridFTP, etc. as well as for job accounting purposes, valid PRACE user credentials and certificates are required for the test user submitting the jobs. It is possible to use existing PRACE staff accounts for this purpose. The proposed UC recommends the use of the DECI project system for UC projects. However, it is not feasible to generate a real DECI project for the purposes of this trial. Instead, a common local test project can be created on all sites involved. In contrast to user credentials, project groups have much less involvement in access and job submission and so this simplification will not significantly lessen the validity of the test. The valid PRACE Staff credentials are being used.

6.4. Data movement

Prior to the launch of a UC job, the input data set(s) must be transferred to the systems on which it will be executed. Depending on the sites involved, this would normally be achieved via SFTP or gridFTP. Utilities commonly installed on all PRACE systems such as gtransfer can also be used for convenience. It would be worthwhile investigating how to best organize the distribution of the data to the exec sites involved. The most obvious approach would be to simply transfer the data from the home site directly to each exec site in turn or in parallel. An alternative would be to stage the data to a dedicated fourth site and then have each exec site download the data sets from here. Similar considerations should be given to data retrieval once jobs have completed.

Data staging has not been validated so far. The assumption was made, that input data is available on the EXEC SITE prior to the start of the computations.

6.5. Local batch system configuration

This represents the crux of the issue in that UC job execution must still be initiated via a batch processing system. However, it is vital that the time between job submission and job execution is minimized. Any production system will typically have a backlog of jobs queued waiting for suitable resources to become available. Only after running jobs have finished and free up resources the highest priority queued job which can fit into the available nodes will be able to be executed. Hence, a specific UC policy will need to be incorporated into the local batch scheduling configuration. Based on a trigger or token indicating a UC job, this special purpose policy can be invoked on a per job basis. This may be simply a specific username, project, queue or QOS label. Once a job requests the UC policy it is up to the local site as to how this is implemented. Some sites may choose to simply apply a very high priority value to these jobs so that they will go to the top of the queue, as it was proposed in SPRUCE publication [1], [6], [10], whereas others may be able to pre-empt running jobs and thus start the UC job almost immediately. Giving higher priorities for jobs is not really an approach for urgent computing, because there is no control when the job will start to run.

- SURFsara - SLURM

The ease with which an urgent computing application can be accommodated by the batch environment is partly dependent on the size of the HPC system relative to the number of cores or nodes required by the urgent computing application. It also depends on the typical job mix for the system, the capabilities of the batch system and policies already in place. At SURFsara the execution system would be Cartesius, the Dutch national supercomputer and PRACE tier-1 system, which uses SLURM as batch system.

The main part of the batch environment governed by SLURM currently consist of 1620 nodes with 24 cores and 64 GiB of memory. 540 nodes have Intel Ivy Bridge cores, 1080 nodes have Intel Haswell cores. The nodes differ somewhat in performance, but are highly compatible. In terms of software stack they are identical and run a Bullx operating system, which is basically RHEL 6 with some vendor specific added value. Jobs can be run over a homogeneous set of Ivy Bridge or Haswell nodes, but also over set of nodes that is a mixture of the two types. These nodes are the standard compute nodes in SURFsara. Standard compute nodes are “resource atoms” in the batch environment and in accounting: standard compute nodes are never shared. A compute job is allocated one or more nodes exclusively. The magnitudes of jobs chosen - 32 cores, 128 cores, and 256 cores - in the environment thus lead to the following resource allocation:

Required cores	Allocated nodes	Allocated cores	Allocated memory
32	2	48	128 GiB
128	6	144	384 GiB
256	11	264	704 GiB

The largest magnitude requires 11 out of 1620 of nodes, which is less than 0.7% and so is relatively easy to accommodate without introducing a pre-emption of jobs – which is, although the batch system would support it, not used in the policies. Job pre-emption leads to wasted compute cycles, disrupted expectations and plans of end users, and to some more complicated job accounting. There is no taboo on job pre-emption, but if it can be avoided by alternative solutions, it should. Given the job mix that is typical at SURFsara and utilizing some of the configuration and accounting features of SLURM, supporting an urgent application is possible without job pre-emption as explained below, at least up to the size of an urgent application that would need 32 of standard compute nodes, i.e., about 2% of nodes or 768 cores and 2048 GiB memory.

The normal job mix at SURFsara is such that there is always a certain demand for some capacity to run relatively short jobs – though not necessarily small in terms of cores – that can be executed quickly one after the other with little queuing time per job. Such jobs are usually associated with development, debugging and testing, or scaling experiments. To cater to these needs, a setup with partly overlapping partitions was proposed. Specifically: short jobs can run on any node that normal jobs can run on and with the same priority. In addition to a backfilling scheduler, which already helps to reduce the queuing time of short jobs, there are 16 nodes (tcn[1-16]) that are only included in the “short” partition, but not in the “normal” partition.

Historically the wall clock time limit for short jobs has varied from 1 to 4 hours, but is currently configured at 1 hour. This implies that the nodes that are configured only as a member the “short” partition can be drained for a reservation or at the disposal for some high priority job in at most 1 hour. This makes them ideal nodes to be included in another overlapping partition, which is only used to run urgent computing jobs.

The following listing shows the SLURM parameters for the Cartesius “short” and “normal” partitions:

```
$ scontrol show partition short
PartitionName=short
  AllowGroups=ALL AllowAccounts=ALL AllowQos=ALL
  AllocNodes=ALL Default=NO
  DefaultTime=00:05:00 DisableRootJobs=YES GraceTime=0 Hidden=NO
  MaxNodes=720 MaxTime=01:00:00 MinNodes=1 LLN=NO MaxCPUsPerNode=UNLIMITED
  Nodes=tcn[1-17,19-35,37-53,55-178,181-898,901-1620]
  Priority=1 RootOnly=NO ReqResv=NO Shared=EXCLUSIVE PreemptMode=OFF
  State=UP TotalCPUs=38712 TotalNodes=1613 SelectTypeParameters=N/A
  DefMemPerNode=UNLIMITED MaxMemPerNode=UNLIMITED

$ scontrol show partition normal
PartitionName=normal
  AllowGroups=ALL AllowAccounts=ALL AllowQos=ALL
  AllocNodes=ALL Default=YES
  DefaultTime=00:05:00 DisableRootJobs=YES GraceTime=0 Hidden=NO
  MaxNodes=800 MaxTime=5-00:00:00 MinNodes=1 LLN=NO MaxCPUsPerNode=UNLIMITED
  Nodes=tcn[17,19-35,37-53,55-178,181-540,573-898,901-1620]
  Priority=1 RootOnly=NO ReqResv=NO Shared=EXCLUSIVE PreemptMode=OFF
  State=UP TotalCPUs=37560 TotalNodes=1565 SelectTypeParameters=N/A
  DefMemPerNode=UNLIMITED MaxMemPerNode=UNLIMITED
```

The complementary partition to which urgent computing jobs can be submitted should like this:

```
PartitionName=urgent
  AllowGroups=ALL AllowAccounts=ALL AllowQos=ALL
  AllocNodes=ALL Default=NO
  DefaultTime=00:05:00 DisableRootJobs=YES GraceTime=0 Hidden=YES
  MaxNodes=11 MaxTime=2-00:00:00 MinNodes=1 LLN=NO MaxCPUsPerNode=UNLIMITED
  Nodes=tcn[1-16]
  Priority=2 RootOnly=NO ReqResv=NO Shared=EXCLUSIVE PreemptMode=OFF
  State=UP TotalCPUs=384 TotalNodes=16 SelectTypeParameters=N/A
  DefMemPerNode=UNLIMITED MaxMemPerNode=UNLIMITED
```

The “urgent” partition shares nodes with the “short” partition, but only those that are not in the “normal” partition and it has a higher priority than the “short” partition. The worst case queuing time of the first job submitted to the “urgent partition” is therefore 1 hour, since that is the maximum wall clock time for jobs running in the “short” partition. If more nodes must be added to partition “urgent”, these must be removed from the “normal” partition.

When, and as long as, there are jobs queued for the “urgent” partition, they will be considered for dispatch before any job queued for the “short” partition. When there are no jobs queued for the “urgent” partition, dispatching jobs queued for the “short” partition to nodes included in the “urgent” partition is highly likely to occur.

Note that, if the urgent computing application must be implemented as a *series* of jobs, rather than a single one, the recipe is to submit the complete series with the first job. If an urgent job finishes before the next job of the series has been submitted, a short job could be allocated some or all of the tcn [1-16] resources and delay the completion of the series with - at most – another hour. Submitting all jobs at once should be feasible for well-prepared, stand-by urgent computing applications.

If specification and submission of all jobs at the start of an urgent computing session is somehow not feasible, such a session cannot simply start with the submission of the first job. Rather, the draining of the nodes in the “urgent” partition and the subsequent creation of an appropriate reservation of these nodes should be triggered. The worst case time for draining these nodes of any “short” jobs is of course also 1 hour. The scenario with a reservation is slightly more complex to implement, because SLURM reservation creation requires administrative privileges. The reservation ID can - and must - be used by the user submitting the series of urgent jobs, but he cannot create, modify, or destroy the reservation.

Access to the “urgent” partition must be restricted to users having appropriate credentials only. SLURM allows the creation and enforcement of associations between accounts, users, and partitions with the help of the `sacctmgr(1)` tool. On Cartesius the specification of such associations on a routine basis to restrict the access of every active user was used + account combination to the partition(s) the account is entitled to use. A user that is allowed to run jobs on all node types typically has 6 associations for the partitions he is allowed to run on:

```
root@mgt3:~ # sacctmgr show association | \
> awk '$3 == "klipdccc" {print $1, $2, $3, $4}'
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc gpu_short
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc gpu
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc fat
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc normal
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc short
sara ncuuh244 klipdccc staging
```

An urgent computing user will be registered with associations only for the “urgent” partition and, as is argued below, probably also to the “staging” partition.

- PSNC - SLURM

Comparing to SURFsara, the queueing system SLURM installed on PSNC’s execution system (called Eagle, holding 90th place in the Top500 list), due to internal policy, has a different configuration where, for example, the wall clock time limit for short jobs is 7 days and the system supports job pre-emption. This is the act of stopping one or more “low-priority” jobs to let a “high-priority” job run. Job pre-emption is implemented as a variation of Slurm’s Gang Scheduling logic. When a high-priority job is allocated then one or more low priority jobs, to which resources have already been allocated, are pre-empted. The low priority job(s) can be resumed once the high priority job completes. Alternately, the low priority job(s) can be re-queued and restarted [<http://slurm.schedmd.com>].

The pre-emption modes available in SLURM are: CANCEL, CHECKPOINT, SUSPEND, REQUEUE depending on the desired action for low priority jobs.

```
ExecHost: eagle.man.poznan.pl
=====
System Name : Eagle
Type : Cluster
Processors : CPU E5-2697 v3 @ 2.60GHz (haswell)
Interconnect : Ethernet 100/1000: InfiniBand FDR
Number of nodes : 1032
Number of cores : 28896
Computing Power : 1.4 PFLOPS
RAM per node : 64/128/256 GB
Storage : Lustre
Operating System : Scientific Linux CERN 6.7 (Carbon)
Queue system : SLURM
```

Excerpt from `slurm.conf` file:

```

...
PreemptMode=REQUEUE
PreemptType=preempt/partition_prio
...

```

The following listing shows the SLURM parameters for the Eagle’s “prace-low” and “prace-high” partitions. Whereas both partitions are based on identical resources (11 nodes numbered from e1021 to e1031) and the former one emulates behaviour of typical cluster’s queuing system partition, the latter enables the user to submit urgent jobs:

```

# scontrol show partition prace-low

PartitionName=prace-low
  AllowGroups=admins,staff,users AllowAccounts=ALL AllowQos=ALL
  AllocNodes=eagle Default=NO QoS=N/A
  DefaultTime=NONE DisableRootJobs=YES ExclusiveUser=NO GraceTime=0
  Hidden=YES MaxNodes=UNLIMITED MaxTime=UNLIMITED MinNodes=1 LLN=NO
  MaxCPUsPerNode=UNLIMITED Nodes=e[1021-1031]
  Priority=10 RootOnly=NO ReqResv=NO Shared=NO PreemptMode=REQUEUE
  State=UP TotalCPUs=308 TotalNodes=11 SelectTypeParameters=N/A
  DefMemPerNode=UNLIMITED MaxMemPerNode=UNLIMITED

# scontrol show partition prace-high

PartitionName=prace-high
  AllowGroups=admins,staff,users AllowAccounts=ALL AllowQos=ALL
  AllocNodes=eagle Default=NO QoS=N/A
  DefaultTime=NONE DisableRootJobs=YES ExclusiveUser=NO GraceTime=0
  Hidden=YES MaxNodes=UNLIMITED MaxTime=UNLIMITED MinNodes=1 LLN=NO
  MaxCPUsPerNode=UNLIMITED Nodes=e[1021-1031]
  Priority=1000 RootOnly=NO ReqResv=NO Shared=NO PreemptMode=REQUEUE
  State=UP TotalCPUs=308 TotalNodes=11 SelectTypeParameters=N/A
  DefMemPerNode=UNLIMITED MaxMemPerNode=UNLIMITED

```

- ICHEC - Torque/Moab

ICHEC’s Fionn system is an SGI ICE X distributed memory cluster with a shared memory SGI UV, Intel Xeon Phi and Nvidia GPU partitions also available via the same login environment. For the purpose of urgent computing applications we will restrict the discussion to the ICE X cluster component. This cluster is comprised of 320 nodes, each with two 12 core Ivy Bridge processors and 64GB memory. Most nodes are diskless but 34 nodes have local SSD disks intended for per-job scratch space. Lustre filesystems on top of a 560TiB DDN SFA12k-20 storage system provide the persistent storage for applications and user data.

The cluster is partitioned into four main areas:

- LongQ nodes (34 nodes with local SSD) Max walltime 144 hours.
- DevQ nodes (8 nodes) Interactive development. Max walltime 0.5 hours.
- MetQ nodes (16 nodes) Exclusively used by the national weather forecasting agency.
- ProdQ nodes (262 nodes) Main production partition. Max walltime 72 hours.

The ProdQ partition is the relevant one for urgent computing applications due to its size although smaller (less than 192 core) jobs could use the DevQ partition and benefit from a quick turnaround due to the short timelimit of regular DevQ jobs. However, these partitions are logical ones and so a dedicated queue for urgent computing jobs can be configured to use include any available node (with the exception of MetQ nodes). This will decrease the wait time for sufficient nodes to become available to enable a job to start.

Job pre-emption is not used in the current environment although it is technically supported by Torque/Moab. Hence, the main method to ensure that a queued urgent computing job runs as quickly as possible is to create a dedicated queue (or class in Moab):

```
CLASSCFG[UrgentQ] DEFAULT.NODESET=ONEOF:FEATURE:DEV,PROD,LONG
```

Assign this queue the highest priority:

```
CLASSCFG[UrgentQ] PRIORITY=100000
```

Then in Torque, create the queue and enable access control:

```
create queue UrgentQ
set queue UrgentQ queue_type = Execution
set queue UrgentQ acl_group_enable = True
set queue UrgentQ acl_groups = urgent
set queue UrgentQ acl_group_sloppy = True
set queue UrgentQ enabled = True
set queue UrgentQ started = True
```

Thus, registered urgent application users and groups can submit jobs to a specific queue and have the jobs run as soon as possible.

- BSC – LSF

Marenostrum III is the current system running at BSC. It is composed of 3052 nodes, 42 of them equipped with Xeon Phi Mic cards and having 128 of them 8GB/core, other 128 4GB/core and the remaining 2796 ones 2GB/core. In terms of projects, BSC have more than 600 projects providing an important diversity of requirements. LSF 9.1 was the queuing and scheduling system elected for supporting BSC back in 2010. It is currently configured with 32 queues including queues belonging to private groups or projects, to PRACE, operations staff, x11, smp, mic, etc.

LSF in BSC is configured using a back fill policy, this means that there is no pre-emption allowed and that jobs are queued following a fair-share priority system. Each queue has a different priority and is added to the user/group priority. BSC cannot apply a pre-emption policy due to the problems that could occur with respect to the SLA provided to BSC's customers when interrupting their jobs. Moreover, a very big persistent storage would be required to flush all job used memory in the time of the pre-emption.

For these reasons, the solution that BSC is able to provide to accomplish the requirements of Urgent Computing is to implement a special queue with increased priority and a big subset of nodes restricted to some users or groups.

At this time, BSC has got a similar queue for quick benchmark tests named "Benchmark".

Its configuration is shown below:

```
Begin Queue
QUEUE_NAME = benchmark
PRIORITY = 199
USERS = bsc99 bsc96452 amp21 usertest
HOSTS = compute mic-loan
BACKFILL = Y
INTERACTIVE = N
EXCLUSIVE = Y
RUNLIMIT = 24:00 480:00
SLOT_RESERVE=MAX_RESERVE_TIME[259200]
HOST_PRE_EXEC = /opt/lsf/9.1/scripts/lsf_prolog
HOST_POST_EXEC = /opt/lsf/9.1/scripts/lsf_epilog
DESCRIPTION = benchmarks jobs
End Queue
```

The fields are self-explanatory, the meaning of the most important ones are:

- PRIORITY=[1-n] : This field indicates the added priority to jobs that are using the queue. In 32 other queues the priority oscillates between 1 and 100. This queue has the biggest priority with the 199 value.
- USERS=[user|group] : This field gives permission only to certain users or groups to use this queue.
- HOSTS=[nodenames] : These are subset of nodes that are going to be part of the queue, for example in this particular case, "compute" indicates that ALL hosts on MN3 are allowed to be selected for jobs submitted to this queue.
- BACKFILL = Y enables backfill scheduling for the queue. A possible conflict exists if BACKFILL and PREEMPTION are specified together. If PREEMPT_JOBTYPE = BACKFILL is set in lsb.params file, a backfill queue could be preemptable. Otherwise, a backfill queue cannot be preemptable. In that case, if BACKFILL is enabled, do not also specify PREEMPTION = PREEMPTABLE.

- EXCLUSIVE = Y specifies that jobs from this queue can run exclusively on a host if the user submits a job with bsub -x.

BSC does not have the parameter PREEMPT_JOBTYPE = BACKFILL so jobs are not pre-emptable.

In order to have the UC requirements satisfied BSC could create a queue like this example:

```

Begin Queue
QUEUE_NAME = urgent
PRIORITY   = 500
USERS      = urgentcomputing_group
HOSTS      = compute
BACKFILL   = Y
INTERACTIVE = N
EXCLUSIVE  = Y
RUNLIMIT   = 24:00 480:00
SLOT_RESERVE=MAX_RESERVE_TIME[259200]
HOST_PRE_EXEC   = /opt/lsf/9.1/scripts/lsf_prolog
HOST_POST_EXEC  = /opt/lsf/9.1/scripts/lsf_epilog
DESCRIPTION    = Urgent Computing Jobs
End Queue

```

Extracted from the documentation there are more interesting parameters for the purpose of UC.

LSF supports PREEMPTION functionality. Here are some useful parameters extracted from the documentation:

```

BACKFILL = Y
enables backfill scheduling for the queue.
A possible conflict exists if BACKFILL and PREEMPTION are specified together. If
PREEMPT_JOBTYPE = BACKFILL is set in lsb.params file, a backfill queue could be
preemptable. Otherwise a backfill queue cannot be preemptable. In that case, if
BACKFILL is enabled, do not also specify PREEMPTION = PREEMPTABLE.

DISPATCH_BY_QUEUE = Y|N
Set this parameter to increase queue responsiveness. The scheduling decision for the
specified queue will be published without waiting for the whole scheduling session
to finish. The scheduling decision for the jobs in the specified queue is final and
these jobs cannot be preempted within the same scheduling cycle.
TIP: Only set this parameter for your highest priority queue (such as for an
interactive queue) to ensure that this queue has the highest responsiveness.

PREEMPTION
Specifies the preemption activity between jobs in this queue and jobs in other
queues. This parameter supports two optional keywords, PREEMPTIVE and PREEMPTABLE.
PREEMPTIVE indicates that jobs in this queue may preempt jobs in lower priority
queues. PREEMPTIVE optionally accepts a list of the names of those lower priority
queues that jobs in this queue can preempt. If no queue names are specified, the
default is to preempt all jobs whose queues' priorities are less than that of this
queue.
PREEMPTABLE indicates that running jobs from this queue may be preempted by jobs in
higher priority queues even if those higher priority queues have not specified
PREEMPTIVE.
E.g., PREEMPTION = PREEMPTIVE[q1 q2 q3]

SLA_GUARANTEES_IGNORE = y | Y | N | n
when enabled allows scheduling within the queue to use hosts or slots held by a
guaranteed resource pool even if this means that some guarantees will not be
satisfied.

TERMINATE_WHEN = [ WINDOW ] [ LOAD ] [ PREEMPT ]
Specifies that the TERMINATE action specified in the JOB_CONTROLS parameter be
invoked when the queue's run window closes, the load exceeds thresholds, or the job
is being preempted so that a higher priority job will run.

MAX_JOB_PREEMPT
Specifies the maximum number of times that a job can be
preempted.

MAX_TOTAL_TIME_PREEMPT = minutes
A job cannot be preempted again after this time which is wall-clock time, not
normalized time. Setting the parameter of the same name in lsb.applications
overrides this parameter; setting this parameter overrides the parameter of the same
name in lsb.params. The default is unlimited.

```

`NO_PREEMPT_INTERVAL = minutes`
Prevents preemption of jobs for the specified number of minutes of uninterrupted run time, where minutes is wall-clock time, not normalized time. `NO_PREEMPT_INTERVAL=0` allows immediate preemption of jobs as soon as they start or resume running. Setting the parameter of the same name in `lsb.applications` overrides this parameter; setting this parameter overrides the parameter of the same name in `lsb.params`. The default is 0.

6.6. Scripting framework to automatically stage data, launch and monitor jobs

In order to reduce the manual steps involved as well as supporting the scheduling of test and validation jobs, as many of the data staging and submission of UC jobs as possible should be scripted. Ideally, only a single command would be required to perform the data staging and job submission on multiple exec sites. Monitoring scripts should be developed to provide feedback on the status of jobs and to retrieve resulting data sets on job completion.

The file staging can be implemented on the LRMS batch script level in the sections: PRE-PROCESSING and POSTPROCESSING (naming conventions differ in each LRMS system).

The authors foresee some manual intervention of the UC Application user in order to run the code on the multiple sites. The deployment of the PRACE-wide resource broker system in this project PRACE-4IP is not foreseen. Depending on the application – any required script for multiple host submission can be created at the user end-point (it can be user station, or their site system).

The variety in types of nodes and the resources available to a system to exchange data with the world outside may vary. Apart from the standard compute nodes Cartesius has other types of batch nodes, in the cluster, but in much smaller quantities, such as 32 “fat nodes” (equipped with 32 Intel Sandy Bridge cores and 256 GiB memory per nodes) and 64 accelerated nodes (extended with 2 Nvidia K40 GPUs per node). But these smaller special purpose sub-clusters will not be made available for urgent computing.

One type of special purpose nodes integrated into the SLURM batch environment is the data staging node, which is equipped with several 10 Gbit/second ethernet adaptors. At SURFsara it would be an option to configure and permanently reserve an interface, or even one complete data staging node as a dedicated data staging resource if that would significantly help the data staging of an urgent computing application.

The staging nodes are similar in their network resources to interactive nodes and by many user of the system staging and archiving of data is done interactively. However, for a number of data intensive workflows it is very convenient if the moving of data can be scripted and run in the batch as well. The SLURM batch system allows the user to express job dependencies. This capability of the batch system is routinely used to arrange that a compute job that needs to process a large amount of staged data does not start until the staging job has completed. Ideally, the urgent computing application takes advantage of these features already in place. The authors recommend urgent computing applications should be fully prepared in “warm stand-by” mode. Data staging job scripts could be in place as well.

7. Summary

Due to the complexity of PRACE-RI, providing uniform configuration of EXEC hosts is not possible, however some hints were mentioned. The operational platform supporting an Urgent Computing case implies that the systems are in a state of “warm standby” for the real event. To fulfil the requirement, the corresponding demands must be addressed:

- All needed application software must be pre-installed
- One or more data sets suitable for validation must be pre-installed
- There must be a validation protocol using pre-installed software and pre-installed data.

^f The data staging nodes are normally operated in shared mode. More than one job is allowed to run at the same time. The nodes have 16 cores and 32 GiB of memory, but the cores are not the crucial resource for the staging jobs. The crucial resources are one or more 10 Gbit/second Ethernet interfaces and the InfiniBand adaptor which hooks the node up to high performance file systems.

- Runs to execute the validation protocol must be scheduled regularly to verify that the applications keep performing as they should, especially after system changes, software upgrades on general purpose and computational libraries, etc.
- Validation runs can be regular batch jobs. A budget of sufficient core hours to perform these jobs regularly must be allocated.
- Since pre-installed software and data may be damaged by human error, or hardware malfunctioning, or even the above noted updating of other software components, there should also be regularly tested procedure to quickly restore – reinstall, relink, recompile, reconfigure, whatever applies – the pre-installed components.

The paper presents the overall discussion on the SLA (Service Level of Agreement) to be concluded between PRACE and external body interested in running Urgent Application. All administrative work and system configurations must be done in accordance with the SLA and other relevant agreements.

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